

RESEARCH ON THE MANAGEMENT OF THE COMMUNICATION PROCESS IN PRE-UNIVERSITY EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Author(s)*: Nicoleta SLABU ¹, Mihaela Luminita LUPU ²
Position: PhD Student ¹, Univ. Prof. PhD. Eng.²
University: „Gheorghe Asachi” Technical University of Iasi
Address: Iasi, Blvd. Mangeron, No. 59A, 700050, Romania
Email: nicoletaslabu@gmail.com ¹, luminitalupu2011@gmail.com ²
Webpage: <http://www.tuiasi.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – The paper considers the importance of external communication at the level of pre-university education institutions in Romania and aims to identify how this is reflected in the relationship with family and community, on the one hand, and in relation to coordinating institutions on the other hand.

Methodology/approach - The methodology approached in the paper consists in structuring the bibliographic study on the aspects presented in the research within the research directions. For the four research directions, a set of objectives were determined, a series of concepts were defined and methods and methodologies were established for each of them.

Findings – The results of this study show the importance of external communication carried out at the level of pre-university educational institutions whose beneficiaries are students, parents and society.

Research limitations/implications – The study presents a research based on the bibliographic study, and the analysed documents are those published by institutions on the official website. A limitation is the realization of this analysis of the process of external communication of the relationship school - family - community and school - coordinating institutions only at a theoretical level.

Practical implications – The study will help to create better external communication between pre-university education institutions and those governing the educational process or other partner institutions.

Originality/value – The main contribution of the study is a model of external communication at the level of pre-university education institutions in Romania.

Key words: communication, management, pre-university.

Introduction

At the community level, the school is the institution whose activity is based on communication, and it is therefore essential that this process, presented by Ross as "always changing, dynamic and reciprocal" (wet. (Panisoara, 2006), to connect with all members of the community in order to adapt to the new realities and to meet the expectations of their pupils and parents.

Analysing the different forms that external communication can have, Annie Bartoli (2015) mentions the existence of three types:

- External operational communication, carried out between the members of the organization with interlocutors from outside the organization;
- Strategic external communication, which consists in building or expanding a communication network;
- External promotional communication (advertising, public relations).

The school is an institution that has various roles: as a mediator between a person and his future, as a mediator between its beneficiaries (children, parents, society) establishing relationships between them, as an intermediary that makes the transition between school and other institutions (family related ,

school, profession). As a result, the school is called to a rapid, profound and continuous change, to a permanent adaptation in relation to the present requirements of the society as a whole. Here comes the need to use different communication channels, especially those based on new information and communication technologies and the opportunities they offer (Totseva, 2015).

Methodology

Through the methodology used, the present research realizes the theoretical substantiation of the external communication within the educational institutions, between the institutions aiming at the educational process and between the educational institutions and partners, establishing the following research directions:

- Researching the communication process within the school-family-community relationship
- Researching the communication process within the school-coordinating institution relationship
- Researching ways to improve / optimize the communication process between pre-university education institutions and those governing the educational process or other partner institutions
- Designing the communication model: school - coordinating institutions

In the research direction "Research of the communication process within the school-family-community relationship" a series of articles and researches from the specialized literature on the regulation of the communication process in the school-family-community relationship were analyzed. The results highlighted various implications of this relationship on students and their families.

The second research direction "Research of the communication process within the school-coordinating institutions relationship" aims to analyze the managerial documents of the institutions targeting the educational process: Ministry of National Education, county school inspectorates, higher education institutions, high school institutions, middle school, primary and preschool. The aim was to establish the way in which the external communication is reflected in the following documents: the institutional development project, the managerial plan, operational procedures.

In the research direction "Research on ways to improve / optimize the communication process between the institutions governing the educational process" the objective aims at diagnosing the existing external communication process at the level of pre-university education institutions, taking into account decisions to eliminate or reduce dysfunctions. reported. For this purpose, the stages that constitute the diagnostic methodology of the external communication process were established.

The latest research direction "Designing the communication model: school - coordinating institutions" aims to build a communication map of the educational institution and develop a model communication procedure, according to the Guide for documented procedures. In accordance to the communication map and the communication procedure, following a research scheme (Figure 1), a communication model will be designed for pre-university education institutions. The emphasis will be on practical aspects and the implementation of the theoretical aspects analyzed above.

The validation of this communication model will be done by concretizing it and taking into account the problems identified following the analysis performed. In the application of this model, the optimization of the communication process will be considered by solving the notified problems and offering recommendations.

Figure 1. Research scheme

Findings

Within any institution in general, and therefore the institutions that govern the educational field, communication is, along with motivation and professional competence, "the key to organizational excellence and effectiveness" (Grunig, 1992). Therefore, the term communication was analyzed from the perspective of several points of view offered by the literature, starting with the definition offered in 1949 by Shannon, C. and Weaver, W in the work "The Mathematical Theory of Communication": " ... the term communication has a very broad meaning, it includes all the procedures by which one mind can affect another. Obviously, communication includes not only written or spoken language, but also music, visual arts, theatre, ballet, and, in fact, all human behaviours. " (Shannon, C., Weaver, W , 1949)

In 1976 American researchers Frank E.X. Dance and Carl E. Larson (1976) identify 126 definitions of communication that they systematize into 15 conceptual classes. It can be seen that this concept offers in the literature many and very diverse approaches, leading to typologies depending on the nature of the message, the speed with which feedback is provided, the number of participants in the communication process, the context of interaction or rigour.

The term "external communication" is used at the level of institutions, referring to the place where interactions take place and all acts of communication. (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Types of communication

Research in the field of communication has led to the emergence of many models of communication. One of the classifications used in the literature is based on the type of relationships between the elements of a communication model graphically illustrated by the authors:

- a) linear models, which regard communication as a linear and one-way process between sender and receiver (e.g. : Shannon and Weaver Model, 1948; Lasswell's Model, 1948);
- b) circular models, which introduce feedback and conceive of communication as a circular process between two or more elements with equal or different capacity for influence (eg: The model proposed by Meyer-Eppler (1963); Osgood and Schramm's model , 1956; DeFleur's model, 1970; Ray Hiebert's circular communication model, Donald Ungurait and Thomas Bohn, 1974; Frank EX Dance's helical model, 1994);
- c) reticular models, which conceive of communication as a network process, in which more than three elements with relevant incidence intervene and which constitute processes of distribution of meaning or information (eg: Norbert Wiener's cybernetic model, 1950; Newcomb's model , 1953; Gerbner's Model, 1956; Westley and MacLean Model, 1957).

At the level of the institution, communication has the role of facilitating the achievement of the general objectives of the organization (Hosu, 2017) which leads to the creation of communication strategies subordinated to the general strategic concepts of the organization.

Within the school-family-community relationship, the parties involved decide to act together in support of the child at the level of the educational process. In this way, partnerships are established with parents, whose roles are "complementary in terms of children's education and ... that children benefit when the home-school relationship is characterized by reciprocity, trust and respect." (Beveridge, 2004).

A multitude of international educational and psychological research from the 1970s to the present attests to the link between parental involvement and children's educational achievements (e.g.: Hewison and Tizard, 1980; Simich-Dudgeon, 1986; Hoover-Dempsey, Bassler and Brissie, 1987; Peterson, 1989; Fine, 1990; Comer and Haynes, 1991; Epstein, 1992; Robinson, 1994; Delpit, 1995; Ball, 1998; Coleman, 1998; Martinez and Velazquez, 2000; Wolfendale and Bastiani, 2000; Hysop, 2001; Christenson and Sheridan, 2001; Weiss and colab., 2005).

The following table presents other aspects that emerged from the research conducted on the relationship between school - family - community:

Table 1. Relevant aspects of the research conducted on the relationship between school - family - community

NR. CRT.	TOPIC APPROACHED	STUDIES / RESEARCH
1.	School-family-community partnerships have significant benefits in terms of students' academic performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Hughes, 1989 ➤ Fan and Chen, 2001 ➤ Epstein 2002 ➤ Jeynes, 2003 ➤ Carter, 2003 ➤ Desforges and Abouchaar, 2003 ➤ Biddulph et al.,2003 ➤ Caspe, 2003 ➤ Redding et al., 2004 ➤ Bryan and McCoy, 2004 ➤ Boethel 2004 ➤ Fisher & Neill, 2006 ➤ Bryan & McCoy, 2007 ➤ Ho, 2007 ➤ Driessen & Smit 2007 ➤ Moore-Thomas & Day-Vines, 2010 ➤ Suárez-Orozco, 2010 ➤ Pinter, 2013 ➤ Pepe & Castelli, 2013 ➤ Muijs, 2015 ➤ Jóhannsdóttir, 2017
2.	The central role of parents in the social literacy of children	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Chern, 2005, ➤ Huang & Wang, 2007 ➤ Ho et al. , 2010 ➤ Wollscheid, 2013
3.	Increasing school attendance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Catsambis & Beveridge, 2001 ➤ Sheldon and Epstein, 2002 ➤ Simon 2004 ➤ Epstein and Rodriguez Jansorn, 2004
4.	Positive effects related to the social adaptation of children	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Jordan, Orozco, Averett, 2001 ➤ Henderson and Map, 2002 ➤ Boethel, 2003
5.	Description of the role of parents in school-family-community partnerships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Vuorinen, 2010 ➤ Krüger and Michalek, 2011 ➤ Ho et al., 2011
6.	Encourage parental involvement in school activities and decision-making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Smith, 2005 ➤ Smith et al., 2007 ➤ Van Velsor and Orozco, 2007
7.	Analysis of strategies used / developed by schools to help and include different types of parents in school activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Bryan and McCoy, 2004 ➤ Moore-Thomas and Day-Vines, 2010 ➤ Vuorinen, 2010
8.	The influence of resources and the socio-economic environment of parents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Abi și Cleghorn, 2005 ➤ Polovina, 2007 ➤ Moore-Thomas and Day-Vines, 2010 ➤ Spernes, 2011
9.	Non-involvement of families belonging to a minority group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Lopez, 2001 ➤ Driessen , 2001 ➤ Suárez-Orozco, 2010 ➤ Pinter, 2013
10.	Personal and environmental factors influence family involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Bandura, 1986 ➤ Van Velsor and Orozco, 2007 ➤ Walker and Shenker and Hoover-Dempsey, 2010 ➤ Moore-Thomas and Day-Vines, 2010

NR. CRT.	TOPIC APPROACHED	STUDIES / RESEARCH
11.	Making comparisons between the level and type of involvement of parents in schools with good results versus parents in schools with poor results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Caspe, 2003 ➤ Desforjes & Abouchaar, 2003 ➤ Gorinski & Fraser, 2006 ➤ Kabarere, 2013 ➤ Averill, Metson, & Bailey, 2016
12.	Lack of knowledge and skills a) Parents ask for teachers' help in their children's development b) Teachers ask for the support of the family in educating the children	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Walker, Shenke and Hoover-Dempsey, 2010 ➤ Brouzos , 1999 ➤ Letch , 1998 ➤ Morris, 1998
13.	Lack of equivalent relationships between parents and teachers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Beveridge 2003 ➤ Lareau 2004
14.	Establishing the relationship between the training and biography of teachers and their attitudes towards the school-family-community partnership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Shartrand et al. ,1997 ➤ Amatea and Clark, 2005 ➤ Smith et al., 2007 ➤ Poulou and Matsagouras, 2007 ➤ Spernes, 2011
15.	Involvement of school counsellors in partnerships with the family	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Bryan and McCoy, 2007
16.	The role of the educator and his relationship with the family	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Amatea and Clark, 2005 ➤ Dor, 2013
17.	Parental involvement is not a priority in many schools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Epstein, 2002 ➤ Cankar and Deutsch, 2009
18.	Analysis of educational policies regarding the school-family-community partnership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Shartrand, Weiss, Kreider, Lopeze, 1997 ➤ Bryan and McCoy, 2004 ➤ Smith et al., 2007; Lin, 2008 ➤ Kristoffersson, 2009 ➤ Vuorinen, 2010 ➤ Moore-Thomas and Day-Vines, 2010 ➤ Dannesboe et al. 2010 ➤ Azaola, 2011 ➤ Ho et al., 2011 ➤ Dor, 2013 ➤ Kabarere, 2013

Within the school-coordinating institutions relationship, the analysis on how external communication is reflected in the studied management documents (institutional development project, management plan, operational procedures) identified the lack of a unitary approach on this issue, at the level of all institutions of education in Romania. On the other hand, a positive aspect observed in some of the schools was the tendency to create collaborations and partnerships according to the needs of the students..

Discussion and conclusions

Following the study of scientific research aimed at the communication process within the school-family-community relationship, two important ideas could be extracted: the first emphasizes the importance that the family must give to the relationship with the school, and the second refers to the ability of the school to adapt to the new requirements of the contemporary family. The works propose some concrete actions through which the family can be with the school. The role of the school, which has the task of initiating communication through which to contribute to the understanding of parents' needs to support their children, is also highlighted.

The communication process between the school and the coordinating institutions is based on several types of connections: coordination, subordination, collaboration, control and evaluation. The communication is made on a legal basis, using public documents. Authorities can monitor whether the

information reaches the beneficiaries in a timely manner, whether it is received correctly, whether it is used for qualitative changes.

The institutional development plans and the managerial plans of several higher education institutions, school inspectorates, as well as at the level of pre-university education were analyzed. The analysis criterion followed the way in which the external communication is reflected in the managerial activity of the educational institutions. It was observed that there is no coherence and an explicit and unitary way regarding the concept of communication, each institution having a different target audience, and external communication, as the main concern reflected in the institutional development plans or managerial plans, does not appear explicitly in managerial documents.

The aim of this study, to create better external communication between pre-university and educational institutions or other partner institutions, has led to the need to set up a model for communication between educational institutions and coordinating institutions/partner institutions.

This study presents a research based on a bibliographic study. The analysis included, in addition to the articles and researches from the specialized literature, also the managerial documents of the institutions aiming at the educational process. A limitation is the realization of this analysis of the process of external communication of the relationship school - family - community and school - coordinating institutions only at a theoretical level. This bibliographic research will be the basis of a scientific support for the research to be carried out in the thesis.

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